

The Myth of the Powerful Consumer:
Deconstructing the Collective Belief

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ABSTRACT

The notion that the consumer is in a position of power relative to corporations is taken for granted by corporations, economists, and consumers in today's mass consumption landscape. This research questions and ultimately debunks the belief in the powerful consumer through (1) the concept of power and sexuality put forth by Foucault, (2) fashion as discourse discussed by Barthes, (3) analysis of French and Raven's uses of power, and (4) consumer interviews. This research shows that consumers are not aware of all the tools for power at their disposal, do not see an alternative to consumption as viable, are unable to extricate themselves from normative dynamics inhibiting their ability to question their position, are trapped by their desires for consumption, and want to see themselves as a powerful entity. Further, this research demonstrates that corporations have the greater power relative to consumers, are invested in perpetuating the myth of the powerful consumer and use their power to reinforce their position. The discussion is concluded by addressing the implications of this research at a societal level, namely in service of sparking a dialog at policy, cultural, and economic levels about power and value.

keywords: consumers, fashion, clothing, power, consumption, capitalism

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Introduction

The notion that the consumer is the powerful entity in the consumer/corporation dynamic is a widely held belief in both academic and business settings. A review of the fields of study focused on the realm of consumer power reveals a pervasive assumption across the research that the consumer is powerful and increasingly so due to various dynamics including the rise of the internet, ease of access to information and the use of social media. In business contexts one encounters notions like 'the customer is always right' and concepts such as consumer sovereignty that reinforce this belief in the wider culture. The idea of consumer power, however, is a myth. The consumer does not actually hold power relative to corporations and the idea that the consumer is powerful is itself a tool for maintaining power dynamics in favor of corporations.

Through an analysis of the facets of power, a historical discussion of the context for consumerism and consumer power, a review of the modern understanding of the powerful consumer, and finally new research into the consumer's perceptions about their own power position, this research aims to deconstruct the widely held western cultural belief that the consumer is powerful. This is in service of offering a new perspective to consumers so that they might reevaluate their positions relative to corporations and seek a more equitable dynamic for their own benefit. Further, this research hopes to restart a discussion that has been dormant for some time about the ideas and impacts of western culture's current simplistic definition of value – economic value, cultural value, and personal value – through the lens of profits and the consumerism in service of those profits.

Power is an expansive and amorphous concept that requires context to best utilize. For the purposes of this exploration, Michel Foucault's ideas in his work *The History of Sexuality, Volume 1: An Introduction* (1978) will be used as a foundational framework to understand the use and methods of power. Foucault's work is also critical to understanding sexuality as a means to the employment of power. Language, class, and desire are important tools at sexuality's disposal for power's implementation.

Fashion and clothing are comprehensively in service of and served by both sexuality and power. The global fashion industry is a multi-billion-dollar business that, at its core, sells sexuality. The business of fashion is fueled by desire: desire to express oneself, desire to be desired, and desire to consume. These desires capture participants in a never-ending cycle that does not resolve in satisfaction for the participant. Through Roland Barthes' work *The Language of Fashion* (2006) we can understand and utilize fashion and clothing as a language unto itself,

and in that a discursive tool for the employment of power. As a discourse, fashion functions much like Foucault mentions – as a tool seemingly in service of the speaker (or wearer in this case), but actually in service to the listener (or provider of fashion, the corporation in this case). In the wearer's need to self-express and participate in the greater culture of fashion, they give up more than they gain including autonomy, true individualism, and economic freedom.

Clothing is, in semiotic terms, mediated as a signifier of social class as well as sexuality. Class and clothing have been linked for seemingly as long as both have existed. From historical sumptuary laws regulating materials and colors amongst classes to modern luxury good signifiers such as a red shoe sole, fashion, clothing, and brands serve as both signifiers of class and gatekeepers of class entry. Though modern laws may offer greater latitude in the regulation of who has access to what items, high costs of luxury goods still serve as barriers to entry for those that wish to participate. These high cost goods are markers of power and the means for power's use.

The intersection of these ideas completes a comprehensive framework through which power, sexuality and fashion can be understood and discussed.

Power Utilization

“Power is tolerable only on condition that it mask a substantial part of itself. Its success is proportional to its ability to hide its own mechanisms.” (Foucault, 1978, p. 86)

Arguably, Foucault's most salient point in his discussion of power is the subtle nature of power. He explains that the power of overt control is limited. It has only the tool of “no” which is blunt and incapable of innovation. The power of “no” cannot overtake the power of creation. Foucault further states that power has its greatest effect when it masks itself or hides its true intentions. For example, in using discourse to examine sexuality and in framing that discourse as an opportunity to alleviate the individual of the burden of their secrets, the illusion is given that power has loosened its grip to allow for such discourse when it has in fact obtained greater hold through increased knowledge and greater supervision. This technique of power employment masks this grab for increased power as an opportunity for freedom for the individual. Foucault argues that power's greatest tool is language, and language is the means and manner of power's hold on sexuality. As mentioned, this is further reinforced by fashion's status as language as put forth in the ideas of Barthes. The dialog that takes place between individual wearers, between a wearer and a company providing clothing, or between a wearer and a

culture through the wearing and use of clothing is highly nuanced and operates within existing power structures. These existing power structures are reinforced by the conversation in which the wearer willingly takes part in order to participate in greater culture, self-expression, and identity definition.

Pursuit of these motivations requires the wearer to subvert their own power – the power to freely express, the power to openly identify – because the tools for expression are owned by the entities in power (in this case corporations and fashion companies). The tools for free expression through fashion are a limited and shared set, thus inherently unoriginal and incapable of free expression. Further, the space available for open identification is guarded by rules and norms that are culturally ingrained making it impossible to be truly open and unfettered in identity seeking.

When power moves from overt *will* to more subtle mechanisms, it embodies itself in the more covert *norm*. Bolder *will* can be undermined, rebelled against. A *will* can be pointed to and isolated. *Will* is exercised by the singular or few, the them to the us. *Norms*, however, are applied by greater society and are woven deeply into the fabric of institutions, classes, communities, and individuals. A *norm* is not easily isolated and often cannot easily be discussed directly but must be talked around. These difficulties make countering or subverting a norm complicated and challenging. Fashion and sexuality are normative and are strong tools at power's disposal. The norm of consumptive behavior, especially within the fashion industry, is perpetuated by the corporations in power whose existence is predicated on the continued consumption patterns of those who seek to be fashionable and express themselves through clothing. To isolate this norm is very difficult and nearly impossible to discuss directly. These dynamics speak to the large amount of power held and utilized by corporations actively utilizing norms to maintain their power position relative to consumers.

Power exerted over an individual or group disguised as empowerment of that same individual or group is power in its most compelling form. This masking dynamic allows the individual or group leveraging power to increase their overall power through the will and actions of the individual or group over which power is being utilized. That utilized individual or group unwittingly seeks to continue the dynamic created by those leveraging power mistakenly believing to do so would benefit themselves when in actuality it is benefitting the individual or group already in power:

“Power is not something that is acquired, seized, or shared, something that one holds on to or allows to slip away; power is exercised from innumerable points, in the interplay of non-egalitarian and mobile relations.” (Foucault, 1978, p. 94)

Power from one point is limited and weak. Power that is made omnipresent through normalization is asserted from all directions and is capable of evolution, which assists in its strength. Within the consumer-corporation relationship and through the understanding of desire, one can understand that the corporation, or seller, has greater power relative to the consumer as the consumer is tethered to their desire. In this dynamic, the seller can choose to produce or not produce, sell or not sell a specific item but a consumer, once trapped in the pursuit of their desire, relinquishes power in order to have the opportunity to fulfill their desire. Once a consumer enters this desire dynamic, they hand over power to the seller or corporation and also become an enabler for their own unchecked consumption behavior fueled by a spiral of increasing desire. This spiral of ever-increasing desire is nearly impossible for consumers to extricate themselves.

The Bourgeoisie

“A normalizing society is the historical outcome of a technology of power centered on life” (Foucault, 1978, p. 144).

“We must say that there is a bourgeois sexuality, and that there are class sexualities. Or rather, that sexuality is originally, historically bourgeois, and that, in its successive shifts and transpositions, it induces specific class effects” (Foucault, 1978, p. 127).

In his discussion of the bourgeoisie, Foucault explores how their focus and infatuation on health, vigor, and life lead to more favorable circumstances for power to gain hold. Prior to the large scale, upper class ideal rooted in the robustness of life, the greatest power explored and utilized by those holding power was the power of death. The ability to kill was supplanted as the greatest use of power by the ability to invest and manage life. He goes on to align the then nascent concept of sexuality with the bourgeoisie's need to seek health and bodily improvements as a way to class elevate. Barthes also discussed the bourgeoisie and their use of clothing items as signifiers for social distinction. Upon the advent of clothing as a commodity during the French Revolution and later solidified by the industrial revolution in Europe and the United States, items of clothing were no longer exclusively made to measure for the wearer but were rather made to a relative standard that the wearer might fit within. This had both a standardizing and democratizing effect for the then dandy bourgeoisie class dressers, forcing them to innovate on the idea of distinction and individualism through norms of wearing instead of the pieces of clothing themselves. These norms allowed for class distinctions with the provided tools for discourse – the mass made, standardized fit garment.

Through these ideas from Foucault and Barthes, parallels can be drawn to the modern Western individual's relationship to clothing and class. The cultural norms influencing ideas of styling and brand allegiance allow individuals to adorn their bodies in ways that mark class lines and signal participation in the bourgeois class – in modern culture known now as the aspirational class. My body is a temple and that's why I will only be seen in Louboutins.

The current bourgeois class, the aspirational class, is a tool for class effects in and of itself. Bourgeois class consumption models the behaviors for all class consumption. Modern life is predicated upon purchasing and consumption; it exists through a complicated web of production and consumption with systems and technologies like sexuality and desire serving to reinforce that web. Fashion is an extreme example of this paradigm; overwhelmingly, product trends come down from upper classes and lower classes seek to emulate or buy into the signifiers of the upper classes.

Power and Capitalism

“This was the first time that a society had affirmed, in a constant way, that its future and its fortune were tied...to the manner in which each individual made use of his sex.” (Foucault, 1978, p. 26)

To create an environment where capitalism can function and thrive, techniques of power must be utilized to control bodies (the means of production) and population (the scale of production). Foucault (1978) puts forth the idea that sexuality itself is that technique. In a capitalistic context, sexuality becomes the means of control of the populations available for producing goods and consuming the goods produced. This cultural norm tells the individual “that its future and its fortune [are] tied...to the manner in which each individual made use of his sex” (p. 26).

Foucault (1978) suggests the idea that power, sex and capitalism have been intertwined since the early stages of the industrial revolution. The transformation of the economies in revolution from need-based transactional to economies dependent on the large-scale production and thus the large-scale consumption of goods that took place during the industrial revolution sought the harnessing of sex as a means to exert power on the means of production: the body.

Foucault notes in *The History of Sexuality, Volume 1: An Introduction* that the need for a robust discourse on sex was primarily in service of population growth for labor and consumption potential and that the discourse successfully recontextualized sex as an economically useful and politically conservative service to the state. Capitalism would not have been possible

without the harnessing of the power of the body for the purposes of production and the harnessing of population for the purposes of growing economies.

“Where there is desire, the power relation is already present” (Foucault, 1978, p. 81).

Desiring, and purchasing to satiate that desire, gives the consumer the opportunity to express themselves and achieve self-actualization in exchange for handing power to the seller. This transaction is not framed as a means of economic enslavement for the consumer, but as a tool for the liberation of the individual. In Foucault’s estimation, the idea of self-actualization through consumption is leveraged by power to assure continued participation in a capitalistic cycle that is not necessarily in the individual’s best interest. The consumption of fashion as a pathway to self-actualization is a self-reinforcing cycle foundationally built on desire. The cycles and seasons of the fashion industry require a perpetual rhythm to support this pursuit of self-actualization. The greatest underlying motivation to desire in this context is to be desired; sexuality has an overt role in desire for the individual but further the desire to be emulated by those around them and the desire to be found relevant by the prevailing culture is not to be understated as reason for fashion consumption participation. In utilizing desire, those in positions of power assure their own interests. Foucault puts a finer point on this argument in his discussion of the deployment of sexuality:

This was the purpose for which the deployment of sexuality was first established, as a new distribution of pleasures, discourses, truths, and powers; it has to be seen as the self-affirmation of one class rather than the enslavement of another: a defense, a protection, a strengthening, and an exaltation that were eventually extended to others...as a means of social control and political subjugation. (Foucault, 1978, p. 123)

The twentieth-century rode on a wave built on the ideas of Marx and Freud. Both Marx and Freud share the core idea that desire is a liberating force. In the thoughts of Marx, the desire to change social and economic class inherently lead to revolution, and in the ideas of Freud, facing desires and taboos liberates from the enslavement by that same desire (Clougherty, 2019). The academic work conducted at the intersection of these principles is best summarized by Jean-Joseph Goux in *Symbolic Economies* (1990) where he examines representation systems across multiple disciplinary and discourse structures including not only the economics of Marx and psychology of Freud and Lacan, but also the theological and sociological. In each of these structures, the representation of power gains such by creating a locus of desire.

While the nineteenth and twentieth centuries may have pushed the idea of desire as liberating, Goux illustrates a shift in that power. Similarly, Frederic Jameson's *Postmodernism* (1991) illustrates that in late capitalism, we have come to understand that desire is not a liberating force, but an enslaving force as it requires consumers to yield power in order to satisfy the desire. While a reader may quickly dismiss this as simply theoretical, a review of literature of the definition and practice of power as reflected within the academic discourse of business as a discipline illustrates that these ideas are empirical as well as theoretical; thereby, setting up the research of this study, with the theory being the primary structure of analysis.

Review of Literature

Power, Status, Hierarchy, and Norms

The dynamic between consumers and corporations is governed by the frameworks of power, status, hierarchy and norms. It is imperative to understand the nature of these frameworks to fundamentally understand the relationship between consumers and corporations and the opportunity for shifts within that relationship.

Power

The most commonly used definition of power comes from French and Raven (1959) and frames power in relation to the influence exerted. They go on to expand the understanding of power through the exploration of 5 bases: reward power, coercive power, legitimate power, referent power and expert power (French & Raven, 1959). Reward power is understood through the ability one individual has to offer rewards to another; coercive power, through the ability one individual has to offer punishments to another. Legitimate power is understood through the perception of one individual that another individual has the right to exert power over them. Referent power is exerted by one individual due to their identification with another individual and expert power is based on the perception that an individual has advanced knowledge granting them expert status (French & Raven, 1959).

Magee and Galinsky (2008) offer some additional layers to the French and Raven definition of power by adding actual power and expanding the conversation around legitimate power. They discuss actual power as functionally manifested control of resources and their allocation; and add to the framework of legitimate power by defining it as independent of actual power and made manifest through use of hierarchy (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Across usage, methodology and understanding, the notion that power begets power and lack of power perpetuates lack of power is shared (French & Raven, 1959; Magee & Galinsky, 2008; Labrecque, vor dem Esche, Mathwick, Novak, & Hofacker, 2013; Wilson, 2018). Power can serve as a 'Felix Felicis Potion'¹. The individual in a position of power can find their way less impeded, the journey easier, the rewards greater and the constraints less when they are in a position of power versus when they are in a place of less relative power. This is possible both because of the reframing of the psychological processes of the individual in power as well as the reframing of the psychological process of third-party actors (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

¹ Also known as liquid luck. Used by Harry Potter in the novel *Harry Potter and the Half-Blood Prince* (2005). A magical potion that, when consumed, improves the luck of the drinker for a period of time leading to the success of all pursuits during that time.

In opposition to French and Raven, Magee and Galinsky (2008) argue that power is not influence, nor is its resistance or conflict. They continue by offering that these concepts are as important as power itself but are secondary effects of power and should be considered separately (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). They offer that influence cannot be the measure of power as influence is potentially immeasurable through accurate means (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). Additionally, Magee and Galinsky (2008) clarify that power can be tacit and does not require active behavior from either the party of greater power or the party of diminished power. For power to be felt, the party in power does not need to influence the party of lesser power nor is it necessary for the party in lesser power to offer active resistance against the party of greater power (Magee & Galinsky, 2008; Labrecque et al., 2013). That being said, power does have limits of both tacit and active use.

The efficacy of power is reduced precipitously when used outside the confines of legitimacy or the range of power (French & Raven, 1959). For example, when an individual in a position of relative less power views the individuals holding power as fair and legitimate, they tend to avoid questioning the situation and help to reinforce the power dynamic (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). However, when an individual in a position of relative less power views those in positions of relative greater power as undeserving or receiving more than their fair share of rewards, they question the legitimacy and thus reduce the efficacy (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Status

Status can be defined as “respect and admiration accorded by others to a target individual” (Magee & Galinsky, 2008, p. 371) and differs from power in that it is wielded and maintained by the observers of power dynamics (Magee & Galinsky, 2008) where power, as previously mentioned, is referential to allocation and ownership of resources. Power and status are referential, causal and reinforcing to one another (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). Power begets status and status begets power; however, both of these concepts can also be understood and used independent of one another (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). In Magee and Galinsky’s (2008) expansion of the definition of power mentioned above, they also broaden the understanding of referent power which they argue is more tied to status than power. Further to the limits of power through the perceived legitimacy of power previously discussed, those in lower status positions suffer more negative consequences when they violate expectations than those in higher status positions. This serves further to reinforce existing power and status structures (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

The maintenance of power structures is served through status. Power relies on the less powerful not questioning the dynamic, as discussed in the limits of power through the perceived legitimacy of power in the previous section. This tacit power relinquishing by the individual in a lesser position of power is maintained through status (or perceived status) of the individual in the position of greater power (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Hierarchy

Power hierarchy, as defined by Magee and Galinsky, is when “individuals are rank ordered with respect to the amount of resources each controls” (Magee & Galinsky, 2008, p. 358). They further clarify a second type of hierarchy, the social hierarchy, as “an implicit or explicit rank order of individuals or groups with respect to a valued social dimension” (Magee & Galinsky, 2008, p. 354). These definitions assist our understanding of hierarchy within the two foundational bases of hierarchy: status and power (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Hierarchy is the game board for status and power to play. Hierarchies are reinforced by the power position held independent of qualifications. Individuals operating within hierarchies often confirm social status-based expectations. For instance, the elevated position of power held by an individual within a hierarchy aids in legitimizing their power, as individuals in positions of less relative power view those in more elevated positions within the hierarchy as deserving and qualified for their power due to their position within the hierarchy (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). These beliefs are held by individuals in positions of relative less power independent of the qualifications of the individual in relative greater power. This self-reinforcing belief both legitimizes power and grants status to those in positions of power within a hierarchy.

Power that is reinforced by an accepted hierarchy causes the power held by the individual and the rules and norms they implement very difficult to change or dislodge (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). In addition and independent to the rules and norms set by individuals in power, individuals in power have ruling power over less powerful individuals because of hierarchy and status allowing them to control behavior inside of the frameworks they are setting for behavior (Milgram, 1974). Individuals in power are able to control both the macro level and micro level of situational dynamics leaving individuals in relatively less power without many tools to change their fate (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Norms

Through their control of situational dynamics and status within a given hierarchy, those in power set norms which are impossibly difficult to change from positions of less power (Magee &

Galinsky, 2008). Power reinforced by hierarchy makes the power held by the individual and the rules and norms they implement very difficult to change or dislodge.

Additionally, with their greater opportunity to get their ideas into the shared norms of any given dynamic, individuals in power are more comfortable exerting their will, further disadvantaging the individual in relative less power who both cannot speak as readily, has fewer opportunities to be heard, and when heard is offered less credibility due to their lesser power position. This dynamic becomes a self-sustaining cycle keeping those with power in power and those without power without (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Value

Through the lens of norms, the perception and understanding of value by individuals in positions of power can be explored. The use of less powerful individuals as a means to goal completion is a power reinforcing cycle manifested by devaluing individuals in lesser relative positions of power and overvaluing those already in positions of power (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). Power allows individuals holding power to reduce individuals in less relative power to functional, non-personal component parts, seeing them overwhelmingly as tools for power use and maintenance. Power allows individuals to see less powerful individuals as a means to an end and not a value or end unto themselves. Power reliably leads to objectification of those in less powerful positions (Gruenfeld, Inesi, Magee, & Galinsky, 2008; Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Behavior

Through an understanding of norms, behavior within power dynamics can be investigated. The possession as well as the presence of power and status affect how individuals behave and interact (Magee & Galinsky, 2008). When an individual is in a position of power relative to others, a psychological sense of control is gained that allows for greater positive outlook and confidence for the individual in power. This mental state, in turn, leads to greater success over the long term for the individual in power. This success leads to a greater perception of available choices over time which further leads to more power for the individual already in a position of power (Anderson & Galinsky, 2006; Magee & Galinsky, 2008). Organizations and cultures tend to over-reward high power and high-status individuals and tend to over-penalize low status and low power individuals, further reinforcing the notion that power begets power (Hollander, 1958; Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Power maintenance relies on the complicity of all parties, both high powered individuals and low power individuals, in order to create a setting where power can take hold (Barreto & Ellemers,

2008; Magee & Galinsky, 2008). Power specifically relies on the complicity of the less powerful in order to exist and grant power to the individuals in the more advantaged position (Magee & Galinsky, 2008; Labrecque et al., 2013).

Communication is an important way in which behaviors are made manifest and power is reinforced (Foucault, 1978; Magee & Galinsky, 2008). For example, individuals in positions of less relative power are able to effectively interpret the notions of those in positions of relative power but the converse is not true (Milliken, Morrison, & Hewlin, 2003; Magee & Galinsky, 2008). Forms of communication and interpretation of the base information lead to further hierarchy maintenance between individuals in power and individuals with relatively less power. The two echelons are effectively speaking different languages which grants opportunity for miscommunication, abstraction, and for those in power to utilize knowledge and information better to their own advantage (Trope & Liberman, 2003; Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Historic Context of Consumerism and Consumer Power

We can map the path to today's relationship between consumers and corporations through five main periods: pre-industrialization, industrialization and the consumer revolution, mass consumption, post-industrialization, and the internet age.

Pre-Industrialization

In pre-industrialized Western societies, purchaser and seller were not contextualized as consumer or corporation. Those seeking to buy goods were simply an individual purchaser, motivated largely by needs (Rezabakhsh, Bornemann, Hansen & Schrader, 2006; Goodwin, Nelson, Ackerman, & Weisskopf, 2008). A seller was an individual or small group of individuals seeking to make a living and provide goods to meet the needs of the purchaser. Selling and purchasing happened within a local dynamic, with the marketplace operating face to face within communities and purchasers making their needs known directly to the seller (Scitovsky, 1962; Goodwin et al., 2008; Edwards, 2014). Though individuals at every economic echelon participated in the purchaser-seller dynamic in the pre-industrialized period, the majority of transactions were happening at the labor class level and thus purchasing decisions were truly weighed against whether items were needed with want playing a diminished role in the individual's decision to purchase (Goodwin et al., 2008). Both purchaser and seller were integral parts of the value chain of the production of goods as purchasers communicated directly with their local sellers about what goods or services were needed and sellers in turn found ways to provide to those needs in order to maintain a livelihood (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). The seller

was reactive to the requests of the purchaser, putting purchaser in the place of greater power during this period.

Industrialization and The Consumer Revolution

Through the time of rapid industrialization in Western societies, experienced in England before the late 18th century and in the United States and other parts of Western Europe before the middle of the 19th century (Goodwin et al., 2008), the individual's role shifted from purchaser to consumer and the seller moved to producer and/or corporation (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). The economic growth that accompanied industrialization was dependent on the creation of goods at an ever increasing scale which in turn necessitated a shift in consumption habits for all members of an industrialized society (Galbraith, 1958; Goodwin et al., 2008; Edwards, 2014) from need based to want based (Katona, 1964; Edwards, 2014). Newly christened consumers entered a paradigm of working for the express purpose of acquiring funds in order to purchase more goods (Goodwin et al., 2008). Accordingly, a shift took place during this period, where goods were purchased increasingly because of the want of the consumer, and not the outright need (Galbraith, 1958; Katona, 1964).

This consumer revolution, beginning in earnest in 1850 and continuing through to 1950 (Flacher, 2005) brought about several prominent theories seeking to explain the power dynamics between the consumer and the corporation. Katona (1960, 1964), Galbraith (1958), Scitovsky (1962) and Mishan (1969) all sought to contextualize economic theories and behavioral psychology theories to better understand consumers.

Katona pioneered survey-based consumer research and formed the Survey Research Center at the University of Michigan which assisted in the formation of his consumer behavior ideas culminating in two of his most influential works, *The Powerful Consumer* (1960) and *The Mass Consumption Society* (1964) (Edwards, 2014). In these works, Katona (1964) put forth the belief that the consumer revolution was a "wholly new phenomenon in human history" (Katona, p.5) that was marked by "consumer power" (Katona, p.5). Katona put little stock by the idea that consumer power had diminished with the rise of consumption and that corporations influenced consumer or consumption habits (Katona, 1964). Katona instead claimed that consumers had never been "sovereign in the sense of being wholly autonomous" and that advertising "contribute[d] to the actualization of certain wants" (Katona, p. 61).

Galbraith (1958), Scitovsky (1962) and Mishan (1969) claim consumer preferences are moot and that producers and corporations have the power and control markets. Additionally, they

claim that through the advent of industrialization and consumer-corporation identity formation, consumer sovereignty had diminished, and consumer wants were not authentic but rather created by the corporations (Edwards, 2014).

In Galbraith's seminal work, *The Affluent Society* (1958), he makes the claim "that the production of goods creates the wants that the goods are presumed to satisfy" (p. 121) and that consumer desires could be "synthesized by advertising, catalyzed by salesmanship, and shaped by the discreet manipulations of the persuaders" because they were "not very urgent" (p. 123). Additionally, Galbraith claimed in *The New Industrial State* (1968) that corporations have incentive to get rid of market influences in order to produce what they want most efficiently (Edwards, 2014).

Scitovsky, through his work "On The Principle of Consumers' Sovereignty" published in *The American Economic Review* (1962), went beyond Galbraith (1958) by positing that corporations are inherently at odds with a true market economy because they would have to serve a more segmented customer base and would lose out on efficiencies and maximum profit. Corporations thus seek to control the market so they can have greater control on what they make and for whom (Scitovsky, 1962; Edwards, 2014). Scitovsky expanded on this concept by stating that in mass production, corporations aim for the average consumer and the average consumer is less informed and thus less powerful, and subsequently more open to influence by corporations and advertisers (Scitovsky, 1962; Edwards, 2014).

In *The Costs of Economic Growth* (1969), Mishan claimed that corporations control the markets and what goods are produced. Corporations seek to persuade consumers to choose what is being produced over their own sovereign wants. Mishan went on to draw the distinction that the economy is not want driven, it is want-creating and the corporations are incentivized to build fashion into products in an effort to engineer planned obsolescence in otherwise usable products (Mishan, 1969).

Mass Consumption

During the period spanning 1950-1980, the economics of mass consumption were taking greater hold in the West with the gross national product of this 30-year period matching the output of the entirety of the 19th century and purchasing power was multiplied by five (Flacher, 2005). This period of increased production correlates to a marked increase in individual consumption and demand for more diverse goods and services to be produced (Flacher, 2005).

More theories were developed to expand understanding of consumer preferences and behaviors, namely the work of Richard Thaler in *Toward a Positive Theory of Consumer Choice* (1980) which shifted focus from economic models framed on normative consumer behavior based on “should” to a model built from observable “actual behavior” (Thaler, 1980; Edwards, 2014). This theoretical expansion into naturalistic modeling led to better insight into predictable consumer behavior for corporations.

Previous to and during this same period, American society maintained a conversation about the risks associated with the rise of mass production and mass consumption, as evidenced in the mid 1960s by publications such as *Business Week*, *The Wall Street Journal*, *Fortune* and *Time Magazine* all expressing concern about the performance of the consumption-based economy and the impact of the economy on the environment, education, government, public works, poverty as well as the need to seek greater meaning beyond material consumption alone (Yarrow, 2006; Edwards, 2014).

Ideological tides were changing during the period of mass consumption, from pro-government interventionists skeptical of unregulated business such as Galbraith in the late 1950s having published *The Affluent Society* (1958) with the previously mentioned work by Scitovsky (1962) and Mishan (1969) continuing through the 1960s, bookended by Galbraith's *The Age of Uncertainty* (1977) manifesting as both publication and television mini-series. This in contrast to free market advocates headed by the Chicago school and Milton Friedman who, in the same year Galbraith published and produced *The Age of Uncertainty* (1977), publicly debated his pro-government ideas and published the collection of those debates in *Friedman on Galbraith* (1977). This reaction and the changing culture lead to increased academic interest in free market economics with a precipitous drop off of the more consumer-oriented ideology of Galbraith and his peers (Edwards, 2014).

Post Industrialization

The era of post industrialization starting in 1980 and spanning until roughly 1995 was marked by small government, pro-corporation ideology in the United States (Bell, 1973; Komlos, 2018). In the vacuum left by thought leaders such as Galbraith, now out of favor, the consumer was left to fend for themselves in a buyer beware free market economic climate (Friedman, 1977; Friedman & Friedman, 1980; Edwards, 2014). Research of this time focused on the consumer as a sovereign, powerful entity in their dynamic with corporations. The concept of a powerful consumer as a driver of economics was first put out by Adam Smith in *The Wealth of Nations*

but further maintained in this era by Friedman (Friedman & Friedman, 1980; Denegri-Knott, Zwick, & Schroeder, 2006).

Advocates of consumer sovereignty make the case that large swaths of independent, well informed consumers have greater power than producers or corporations (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006). Consumers are presumed to act self-interestedly and rationally within the paradigm of consumer sovereignty (Goodwin et al., 2008). Their power is manifest in the 'invisible hand' of the aggregate consumer choice guiding the overall market and is amplified when forces are combined with other independent consumers to exert pressure on corporations to act as consumers dictate (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006). The idea of the powerful consumer helps to maintain the low-regulation, corporation-friendly climate of this time period; a powerful consumer deflects potential responsibility from that of corporations to the will of the consumer and the free market (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006).

Internet Age

With the advent of the internet into common use through the 1990s, the nature and role of the consumer changed. The internet facilitated the ability of the individual consumer to make purchases across geographic spaces previously non-navigable except to the exceptionally wealthy and offered a shift in the range of choices that a consumer now had (as evidenced by Chris Anderson in *The Long Tail: Why the Future of Business is Selling Less of More*, 2006). While many have seen the transition as an empowerment of the consumer the real effect was in the relationship of the consumer to information. The access to information is not power in itself; it is only the appearance of power as access gives only an opportunity for a pathway to power.

The internet certainly changed power dynamics between consumer and corporation through the swift facilitation and widespread access of information allowing both consumer and producer to be more informed, reducing historical information asymmetries (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). By way of the internet, consumers were granted access to greater information, corporations were afforded easier and cheaper means through which to share information, and third-party advocacy groups were given the ability to connect and facilitate greater market transparency (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006).

The conversation between consumer and corporation was further empowered through the advent of the internet and associated technology. This discursive power model rejects the sovereign consumer and the antagonistic dynamic between consumer and corporation and speaks to a cooperative process between the two parties of norm creation and ideation

(Denegri-Knott et al., 2006). This ongoing dialog between consumer and corporation leads, in theory, to the development of mutually held truths and an environment where consumer is neither powerful nor powerless but rather a co-conspirator in the mutually developed consumption practices (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006). To participate in this dynamic, consumers sacrifice privacy and pocketbook to be able to contribute their voice to corporations and to be participatory to the product development process (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006; Labrecque et al., 2013). To expand upon the idea of the consumer as participant in consumption norms as facilitated through internet technologies, former Harvard professor Douglas Holt states that “rather than a revolutionary vanguard, such consumers are more accurately theorized as participants in a countercultural movement that, working in concert with innovative firms, pursued market-based solutions to the contradictions of modern consumer culture” and goes on to say that “what has been termed “consumer resistance” is actually a form of market-sanctioned cultural experimentation through which the market rejuvenates itself” (Holt, 2002, p. 89).

Today

With the advent of the internet and greater access to information and diverse product, consumers are once again contributing to the value chain of a product through dialog with corporations, collective sanction power, co-marketing and co-developing (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). Though certainly there is conversation regarding the oppressive nature of consumption and marketing, postmodern consumer researchers tend to theorize consumption as an opportunity for resistance and freedom for the consumer in their dynamic with corporations (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006).

In current research and conversations, it is largely assumed that the consumer is in a very powerful position versus the corporation (Denegri-Knott et al., 2006; Rezabakhsh et al., 2006; Edwards, 2014). The idea that current consumer paradigms have created more consumer power is treated as a foregone conclusion insofar as it is not be deeply researched or tested (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006).

The Powerful Consumer

Within current literature and professional discourse, it is assumed that the consumer is in a position of power relative to the corporation. Different sources leverage different frameworks and perspectives as to the means of that power including information-based power, demand-based power, network and crowd-based power, sanction power, and legitimate power.

Information-Based Power

Technology generally, and the internet specifically, have facilitated both the quantity and quality of information available to the general public (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006; Wilson, 2018).

Before technology driven information access, consumers historically had less power in the market and in dynamics with corporations due to high costs of information and high information asymmetries (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). The idea of historical information asymmetries between consumers and corporations has not been extensively researched or reported on because most studies have instead focused on the costs of buyer search and the effect on market prices (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). This relatively new access to knowledge has increased the perception of control for consumers relative to corporations (Labrecque et al., 2013); however, that perception only allows the consumer to feel as if they have more power but the shared aggregate information that consumers utilize to become more knowledgeable is in turn shared with the corporation who use to their own advantage in order to better understand consumer behaviors and motivations. This allows corporations to pivot quickly to changing consumer behaviors and manipulate consumers to greater and further consumption ends (Galbraith, 1958; Scitovsky, 1962; Mishan, 1969).

Information-based power is comprised of two facets: power through content consumption and power through content production. Information-based power through content consumption relates to consumers' access to product or service information. This power reduces information asymmetry, expedites market diffusion of information and shortens product life cycles (Labrecque et al., 2013). Today, consumers are assumed to be better educated and more sophisticated than their historical counterparts due to their ability to access and consume more information than was available previous to the internet (Labrecque et al., 2013).

This information and power boon for consumers is not without its caveats. It is necessary to understand that although consumers have wider access to information thus reducing previous asymmetries with corporations, the information that is available is overwhelmingly managed and curated by corporations. Often information is shared or discussed through corporation owned platforms thus negating the laissez faire open market ideal of actually free information. Information is edited, curated and managed by the corporations and the consumer sees only what the corporation is comfortable allowing them to see (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Information-based power through content production focuses on the ability of the consumer to produce user-generated content. It facilitates consumer empowerment by providing an outlet for

self-expression, extending individual reach, and elevating the potential for individual opinion to influence markets and corporations (Labrecque et al., 2013). Content production for the consumer can be a means to publicly discuss undesirable products, performance, policies, or behaviors of corporations and shifts power from the marketer and corporation to the consumer. Specifically, online product reviews have been a massive opportunity for consumers to claim and utilize power from corporations and receive more of what they desire from the market (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Consumer content production is consumer-centric and based in self-expression, but the content produced can be used by a corporation for their own ends (Labrecque et al., 2013). The result of user generated content is shown to improve the financial standing of a corporation should they be utilizing the information and content created and shared by consumers effectively (Labrecque et al., 2013).

In creating and sharing so much content online, consumers are able to be profiled on search history, lifestyle, and purchase behaviors, giving corporations access to their private lives in order to have a means of self-expression and an open dialog with those corporations (Labrecque et al., 2013). Though consumers are relatively tolerant of relinquishing their privacy in this dynamic with corporations, there is a growing limit to their openness. As defined by French and Raven in their 5 bases of power, expert power is based on the perception that one party in a dynamic has some special knowledge or expertise relative to another (French & Raven, 1959). Stated differently, expert power relies on information asymmetries (Wilson, 2018). It is understood that when one party believes that another is better informed, they are more apt to accept the expertise of that second party (Wilson, 2018).

Historically, expert power was overwhelmingly in the hands of corporations as consumers had no easy access to information and the cost of gathering was very high (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). In a traditional corporation-consumer relationship, corporations have the means to access and acquire more information than consumers resulting in expert power in the hands of corporations (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006; Wilson, 2018). The expert power of companies has decreased, however, with the advent of technology-facilitated information sharing resulting in increased levels of market transparency for consumers (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). As increased access to technology continues to proliferate the culture, consumers become ever savvier of the means to control their own data and user generated content. This management and understanding of their own information assists in further consumer empowerment, allowing consumers to become product experts and exert increasing amounts of expert power

(Labrecque et al., 2013). As always, there is a limit to this increased expert power for consumers. The idea that an individual becomes an expert after a certain time investment in a singular activity, called the “10,000-hour rule” by Malcolm Gladwell in his 2008 book *Outliers*, opens a conversation about consumer information contribution relative to corporations. For voracious consumer product reviewers, a tipping point exists where the consumer information producer moves from more educated and more powerful in their dynamic with corporations to stooges for the corporation thus handing over the entirety of their power (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Lastly, it should be said that the power afforded to consumers by increased access to technology facilitated information only applies to consumers with access, understanding, and means to participate in technology. Consumers with limited access to information do still benefit from greater overall consumer agency and power but at the same time those handicapped by lack of information access by way of technology weigh down the total power potential of consumers.

Demand-Based Power

Demand-based power functions in the collective purchase behaviors and consumption habits of an individual consumer. The concept of demand-based power existed before the internet and other associated technologies, but today is largely facilitated by the internet (Labrecque et al., 2013). Consumers use their power in this framework through voice and exit, directly requesting the things they want or need, and when not acted upon by companies, effectively take their spending power and go. This ability for consumers to demand what they want directly to companies has led to a wider breadth of products offered by companies (Anderson, 2006). This broader assortment in turn makes marketer’s task more challenging as consumer attention is more difficult to acquire and is given to marketers in shrinking amounts leading to a relative increase in consumer power (Labrecque et al., 2013). Though this framework allows for an increase in consumer power, the greatest power a consumer is afforded is the power to not consume. Anything else is a dynamic that gives corporations as much as the consumer perceives they gain in power (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Network and Crowd-Based Power

Network-based power for consumers is a multi-way dialog manifesting in the actions of consumers adding value beyond the original content in order to influence others (Labrecque et al., 2013). Within the framework of network-based power, consumers have an opportunity in today’s economic landscape to exert power through influencing networks and co-creating with

corporations. Consumers influence their personal networks by way of technology driven social networks such as Facebook, Instagram and any number of ever evolving others. These modern technology-driven networks allow for fast communication uninhibited by proximity and empowered by access to information. Historically, before the advent of the internet, consumers relied on traditional word of mouth methods which were highly dependent on face to face interaction and were limited and impeded by geography (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). Network based power increases the efficacy of both information-based power and sanction-based power through the widespread dissemination of user-generated content via influential consumers within a given network (Labrecque et al., 2013). The idea of consumer-corporation co-creation centers around the concept of shared responsibility for value creation between corporation and consumer leading to more synergistic outcomes for both parties (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Consumers have the opportunity to participate in the value creation of a product and have their voice heard by a corporation at the inception of a product, not just at the marketing stage. This multi-way open dialog differs from information-based power content production which is a one-way broadcast focused on self-expression (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Though network-based power is an impactful and far-reaching tool at a consumer's disposal, it is tempered by the power it also affords corporations. Influential network participants stump for a corporation in discussing a product, offering a more authentic, wider reaching, and more effective advertisement than traditional marketing could have accomplished (Kratzer & Lettl, 2009; Labrecque et al., 2013). Corporations recognize and strategically leverage network influencers' ability to speed up the product adoption process, increase the size of a market for a product, and predict product success (Labrecque et al., 2013). Co-creator consumers also assist in the maintenance of corporate power by willingly participating in the discursive process, offering corporations a better understanding of consumer motivations which can then be utilized to manipulate the consumer (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004; Labrecque et al., 2013).

Crowd-based power partners with the concept of network-based power in relying on the pooling of resources in order to achieve an outcome (Labrecque et al., 2013). The concepts of network-based and crowd-based power rely on all power opportunities that proceed it in discussion including information-based power, demand-based power, and network-based power and amplifies the impact of those opportunities (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Sanction Power

The power of consumers to sanction corporations is a well understood economic theory that can be explained as a means of disciplining a corporation's behavior should a corporation not

respond favorably to a consumer's interests. Both exit and voice are major functions of sanction power (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). The idea of consumer sanction power assumes that individual consumers, without greater coordination with one another, can affect macro-level changes from corporations by impacting sales through exiting to another supplier (Gintis, 1989). Historically, before technology-driven information sharing, consumer sanction power on corporations through the use of exit had limited effectiveness due to lack of transparency in sanction behavior and in lack of alternate suppliers in a less diversified market (Hirschman, 1970; Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). Voice also had historical impediments in sanction power use as, previous to the advent of technology-based information sharing, there were no platforms to effectively share consumer perspectives and any consumer dialog with corporations operated in private channels and was easily hidden by corporations (Hirschman, 1970; Pitt, Berthon, Watson, & Zinkhan, 2002; Rezabakhsh et al., 2006).

The rise of Internet commerce and internet facilitated information has empowered consumers through expanded product offerings, increased supplier options, and new service opportunities (Day, 2011) making exit an increasingly viable sanction option as well as through platforms allowing the effective use of individual and collective voice for consumers to publicly share feedback with corporations (Pitt et al., 2002). Consumers' sanction power has increased as the internet facilitates the effective use of exit and voice (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Legitimate Power

Legitimate power occurs when one party is inferior to another and the inferior party accepts the influence and legitimacy of the superior party (French & Raven, 1959; Wilson, 2018). The legitimate power of consumers has been strengthened by their growing authority and influence in the value chain through voice, co-creation and discussion with corporations (Rezabakhsh et al., 2006). Today, consumer preferences are driving price paradigms through demand for wide product assortments delivered by way of ever diverse distribution channels, illustrating a perceived value of consumer input by corporations (Labrecque et al., 2013).

However, if the willingness of corporations to value consumer input indicated strongly the consumer's power position over corporations, these price paradigms would exclusively be in consumer's favor. This is not the case as willingness to pay and the customer's perceived utility often allows corporations to charge more than production price benchmarking would have signaled (Porter, 2000; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004; Labrecque et al., 2013). In reality, the increased dialog between consumers and corporations allows corporations to better understand consumer motivations and thus use that knowledge for their own ends, including increasing

costs in the favor of corporations (Labrecque et al., 2013). Inviting consumers to participate in the product development process is further use of this dynamic in favor of the corporations while making consumers believe they are powerful enough to drive the process (Labrecque et al., 2013).

Methodology

Though a review of historic and current research lends much to the understanding and discussion of consumer power, ultimately it seems prudent to ask the consumer themselves what they think of their position. This largely seems to have been avoided in current research methodologies. This simple dialog has the potential to relay both the overt answers to the questions asked and also give insight to the more complex systems that influence consumer power with or without their awareness.

The research conducted aimed to ask the consumer directly how they see their relationship to corporations and understand their perceptions of their own power versus the power of corporations. The goal of this work is to examine the assumption that the consumer has power in their dynamic with corporations as well as to understand whether the average consumer perceives themselves as having power in that dynamic.

An additional goal is to challenge the body of work supporting the assumption of the powerful consumer as the nature of the means of collection in previous research has been managed through existing power structures which, as discussed, is inherently biased towards those in power, thus skewing the results. The greatest achievement this research could obtain is to initiate a reputable discourse about the way consumers are perceived, the way business is conducted in the most general terms, and assist in the ideation of a new way of conducting business where power is more equitable between consumers and corporations, resulting in better holistic long term outcomes for economies and societies.

Research Design

This study used a qualitative approach to gather research from a statistically relevant number of consumers about their perception of power held between themselves and corporations. Interviews were impromptu and in public spaces proximate areas of high quantities of clothing consumption. The means of the qualitative approach was specifically built to subvert the potential power imbalance between interviewer and interviewee that would potentially be established in a more formal setting. To obtain answers that are as unguarded and honest as possible from consumer subjects, the interviewers sought to present as humbly as was possible while still maintaining professional credibility. This includes manner of dress (clean and well-groomed but not wearing items associated with business or power including suits, strong shoulders, high heel shoes, or monolithic black or gray colors), professional signifiers (eschewed use of business cards, name tags, or professional recording equipment), and

manner of conversation (used colloquial language, seemed friendly, aimed for a perception of openness). The means of data collection was designed to aid in the perception of interviewee empowerment due to the fact that the interviewer must approach a stranger knowing they could be rejected.

Methods of Research

One-hundred subjects were chosen at random by two interviewers, one female and one male, over a 3-day period in high fashion consumption areas of New York City in May of 2019, including 5th Avenue near 59th Street, Rockefeller Center in midtown Manhattan, and Troutman and Wyckoff Avenues in Bushwick, Brooklyn. Subjects were approached by an interviewer and asked to participate in a five-question interview with an estimated completion time of 2 minutes. Subjects were asked permission to be recorded on the interviewer's iPhone.

Interview Questions

Each random subject was asked five questions in the order listed below. To ensure each subject was in fact a fashion consumer, Q1 was offered as a screener so as to eliminate any assumptions despite the nearly ubiquitous nature of clothing consumption in the United States.

Q1: Have you bought an item of clothing, shoes or accessories in the last 6 months?

Q2: What power do you believe you have as a fashion consumer?

Q3: Do you believe that fashion brands to which you are loyal care about your preferences?

Q4: Do you believe that you have the ability to change the way that a fashion brand operates?

Q5: Do you believe that consumers acting together can have a measurable effect on the behavior of corporations?

Objective

The aim in conducting short form interviews with a wide range of unprepared subjects was to capture the greatest basic understanding of consumers' perception of their power when they were likely to offer the greatest amount of candor to the interviewer while in a setting of close physical proximity to the manifestations of clothing consumption. These conditions were chosen to make conversation as conducive as possible to the subject of fashion consumption for the chosen subjects.

Recruitment

Subjects were chosen at random; however, some guidelines were utilized. A conscious effort was made to choose subjects of varying ages, ethnicities and assumed genders within the 100 interviewees and potential subjects with conspicuous shopping bags were favored. Potential subjects were avoided who were assumed younger than 18 years of age.

Methods of Analysis

Responses were reviewed and analyzed for topline binary answers in the affirmative or negative to each question, though a middle answer of “maybe” was accepted. Additionally, more qualitative analysis was used to note nuances in perception, feelings, and manner of individual responses and patterns in the qualitative analysis were analyzed across the entirety of the data collected. The most inherently qualitative question, Q2 “What power do you believe you have as a fashion consumer,” was analyzed separately to understand and infer what tools for power leveraging consumers understand to be at their disposal in their dynamic with corporations.

Findings

Analysis of the 100 interviews yielded many nuanced results but the general consensus from consumers is that the majority do not feel they hold power as individuals relative to fashion corporations. This sentiment for the individual generally increased as the questions progressed and increased in specificity. The only area where consumers agreed en masse and overwhelmingly believed in their own power is the power held by consumers acting together.

Statistics

Of the 100 individuals interviewed, 67 were assumed to be female and 33 to be male. Eighty percent of responses were collected by the primary researcher (white, female, mid 30s) and 20% by the research assistant (white, male, mid 30s). The majority of responses, 63%, were collected at or near the 59th Street and 5th Avenue location followed by 24% at Rockefeller Center, 8% in Bushwick, Brooklyn and 5% at Madison Square Park. The quantitative responses to all 5 questions break down as follows in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1

Quantitative Responses to Interview Questions

	YES	NO	MAYBE
Q1: Have you bought an item of clothing, shoes or accessories in the last 6 months?	98%	2%	0%
Q2: What power do you believe you have as a fashion consumer?	47%	53%	0%
Q3: Do you believe that fashion brands to which you are loyal care about your preferences?	36%	60%	4%
Q4: Do you believe that you have the ability to change the way that a fashion brand operates?	31%	65%	4%
Q5: Do you believe that consumers acting together can have a measurable effect on the behavior of corporations?	92%	2%	6%

Acknowledging the Disadvantaged Position

Though there was nuance and conversation in the Q2 affirmative responses regarding what power the interviewee felt they have as a fashion consumer relative to corporations, the 53% of respondents that answered negatively were nearly monolithic in their answers with responses such as “none”, “zero”, “not much”, and “very little” dominating the response data. This negative response trend regarding the individual consumer perception of power held by consumers increases progressively across the interview questions through Q4, increasing from 53% in Q2 to 60% in Q3 and topping off at 65% in Q4.

In reviewing the qualitative responses to the interview questions, some shared ideas across all responses were found and able to be correlated. For Q3 responses, the most robust trend within negative responses was the idea that “brands do their own thing and do not care about what I want” as a consumer. This is evidenced in the below responses:

“[The brand] offers you what you want, and you will also change according to their changes. So, I feel like, in that way, they don't really need to, like, comply to you. You're basically like a pretty passive consumer.” (R4, Q3)

“I feel like the brands pretty much do their own thing and you buy it or not. I don't feel really listened to as a consumer. But maybe it's also because of the brands that I choose.” (R10, Q3)

“You find something you really like and [the brands] go with the trend, like 'oh everything's 2 inches shorter this year' so they make it 2 inches shorter. For what?” (R56, Q3)

The Power of Choice

Supported by the responses to questions Q2 through Q4, the greatest power consumers in this study feel they have as individuals is the power of choice and/or exit. The greatest portion of the responses in this trend occur in Q2.

“What power do I have as a fashion consumer? Well I think I have ultimate control over my own choices and fashion decisions. So personally, I think as an independent person I think I feel pretty good about that.” (R6, Q2)

“Quite a bit [of power], I guess, especially if you are making smart choices with how you're purchasing fashion.” (R8, Q2)

“I have all the power. I choose.” (R46, Q2)

“I think you have the power with your dollars and so where you choose to spend your money kind of indicates where you have loyalty either towards a company or towards a particular lifestyle.” (Q55, Q2)

“All the power. We have the right to consume as we want to. So, we can either consume smart or consume ignorantly so it's all within our power.” (R73, Q2)

“If I don't believe in what the producer stands for, what they do, or how the things are produced I don't buy from them. Purchasing power, I suppose.” (R76, Q2)

A total of 22 qualitative responses out of a total of 171 qualitative responses across all questions spoke directly to consumers' power of choice and/or exit.

“Because if I don't like it, I'm not going to buy it, and I've done that with brands. They've changed their brand, so I've switched to someone else and the more people do that they're not going to do that.” (R57, Q4)

“Just by being honest about the things that they sell, and if I'm not happy about it their sales will go down.” (R91, Q4)

Power in Numbers

Across questions Q2 through Q5, an overwhelming trend in attitudes towards consumer power was the discussion of the power of collective consumers. Ninety-two percent of respondents to Q5 answered positively to the question of whether consumers acting together had power relative to corporations. This culminates in the idea of collective power peppered through interviewee responses to Q2 through Q4.

“I think that as an individual it's tough to feel that you have a ton of power but if you're part of a group that is, say, boycotting a brand or has brand preferences one way or another then you feel a little bit more powerful. But I know that, like, walk into Macy's going to one brand versus the other I don't feel that I have a ton of power in terms of how that's going to affect things in a broader sense.”

(R89, Q2)

“They don't care about our preferences; they care about the masses' preferences as a whole.” (R54, Q3)

“As a single customer, I really don't think so. It's just, you know, numbers make sense. If several people, or millions of people, think in similar ways or they have similar preferences then yes, but as a single customer, I really don't think so.”
(R43, Q4)

This concept of power held by consumers is the largest shared concept across all positive and negative responses throughout all questions. A total of 19 qualitative responses correlated to this trend across questions Q2 through Q4 out of a total of 171 qualitative responses for those same questions, in addition to the overwhelming majority response for Q5 already mentioned.

Cognitive Dissonance

Though the 47% affirmative response to Q2 is not insignificant, the qualitative discussion of Q2 reveals a potential cognitive behavioral gap and a cognitive dissonance for consumers who believe in their own power relative to corporations. This phenomenon is not specific to the more qualitative inquiry of Q2, though this question did result in the greatest number of cognitively dissonant responses; it repeats through all remaining questions through Q5 within responses from interviewees. This manifests in a positive quantitative response followed by a qualitative response in discord to the initial positive quantitative response.

In Q2 responses, there were 8 responses within affirmative quantitative responses that showed a discord between the quantitative and qualitative responses. The reasoning differed by respondent, but the disparity was consistent. Examples include the following:

In response to the question “What power do you feel you have as a fashion consumer?”

“Oh yea [I feel I have power]. But I don't know why.” (R24, Q2)

“I think that we do have the power to choose. You know if I either want to buy something that is like plastic versus not or, I guess, I have the power to choose where I spend my money. I don't think that necessarily dictates the kind of factories or the work that is done but it's something.” (R98, Q2)

“I think you have to at least know where it's from and all that so you can make a good choice.” (R34, Q2)

“There are some limits, some caveats. Wanting to look good but also being like ahhh price does matter. So, I think that's maybe some limits to that power. It's a matter of priorities, and I could shift my priorities.” (R74, Q2)

Further example of the disconnect between initial positive affirmation followed by a more complex qualitative response include the following:

In response to the question, “Do you believe that fashion brands to which you are loyal care about your preferences?”

“I feel like I am loyal to like 3 brands. I think those 3 are pretty aware of me. And then there are some that are guilty, and I am not loyal to them but I'll shop there. And I feel bad about it.” (R74, Q3)

In response to the question, “Do you believe you have the ability to change the way a fashion brand operates?”

“Minimal. We buy a lot of secondhand and that kind of stuff.” (R8, Q4)

“Yes, if we are not alone. If we made a boycott.” (R33, Q4)

“It depends on the brand. Not all brands will focus actually on the actual customers. They'll focus on the trends. They'll make whatever is trendy and then they'll just put it out there and then it goes to what he said [R83] you either follow it, you buy it or you don't buy it.” (Q84, Q4)

In response to the question “Do you believe that consumers acting together can have a measurable effect on the behavior of corporations?”

“Together, yes. But the problem is getting them together.” (R65, Q5)

A more specific manifestation of this phenomenon was evidenced in responses that spoke to the normative judgment of what should be happening in the power dynamic between consumers and corporations.

“I think it's interesting...it's fashion and as a consumer they really want us to buy their product, right, so they have to care about what I think about or what I'm interested in.” (R6, Q3)

“I would say they should be if they want to keep clients or customers.” (R8, Q3)

Limitations and Future Research Directions

The conducted research has several limitations to consider. Due to time constraints, only 100 subjects were interviewed, and additional research would benefit from larger interview pools to confirm the data found in this study. Further, the research in this study limited the number of

questions to 5, as discussed, and could benefit from additional and more specific interview questions. Lastly, the research in this study was conducted over a short period of time in a singular region. Further research could expand to seek responses from more diverse regions including rural, suburban and urban areas with a diversity of consumerist-oriented locations such as shopping malls, outlet malls, and pedestrian heavy urban areas.

For impromptu research, male interviewers potentially are in a disadvantaged position in pursuit of permission from strangers to conduct an interview. In the same span of time that female researcher 1 was able to interview 67 subjects, male researcher 2 was only able to gain permission from 20 subjects. Female researcher 1 only received a single outright “no” from strangers when requesting their time for the interview where male researcher 2 received more than was counted. This research would suggest favoring female interviewers for any future research of random individuals in a public setting.

Discussion

The idea that the consumer is powerful permeates business, academia and the greater culture, and through that ubiquity becomes a normative concept. The universality of this belief makes for a more difficult discussion but does not mask the reality that this belief is incorrect. The concept of the consumer as a powerful entity in relation to the corporation is a myth. Through the understanding of power, the tools available for its employment, and the attitudes of consumers, it can be seen that current ideas of consumer power are merely a diversion tactic to redirect from the actual dynamic between consumers and corporations. Corporations hold the greater power and utilize the tools of norms and culture to wield and maintain that power in order to ensure their continued existence and growth, often at the direct expense of consumers.

Power That Is Not Acknowledged Cannot Be Utilized

Consumers are not aware of their options for empowerment, and thus cannot be utilizing their power. Per Foucault (1978), it is understood that power that is not known cannot be exercised. Through the academic understanding of consumer power, taking advantage of French and Raven's (1959) definition as well as the expansion of that definition by Rezapakhsh, Bornemann, Hansen, and Schrader (2006), the opportunities and under-utilized means for consumer power can be discussed.

Information-Based Power

The idea of information-based power is one of the most thoroughly discussed and academically researched areas of consumer power with focus increasing with the advent of the internet and its analogous technologies. In academic discussion, this consumer power opportunity is heralded as the greatest growth area of power available to consumers. The research conducted here offers a stark contrast; interview subjects did not speak to this opportunity. Increased access to power that can be utilized to make more informed decisions and potentially increase the leverage consumers have in relation to corporations was not acknowledged as a perceived opportunity or means of power by the interview subjects. Though this may be a theoretical means for empowerment for consumers, and independent of acknowledgement by consumers may offer them some tools in their favor, if the consumer does not view it as a means to increase their power and does not actively use it as a tool to acquire power, then it is not contributing or aiding in the consumer's relative power.

Demand-Based Power and Sanction Power

An area of consumer power that was understood and acknowledged in this research by the subjects was demand and sanction power. Use of voice and exit were cited frequently among interview subjects that responded in the affirmative to the question of what power consumers had relative to corporations. This presented in the concept of consumer choice. Though the tools of voice and exit are useful to consumers in dynamics with corporations, without the interplay of all other areas of consumer power in active use and without the threat of actual exit from the consumption cycle, they are somewhat limited means for consumers to use in relation to the arsenal of tools at the disposal of corporations.

Crowd and Network-Based Power

Crowd-based power was the most uniformly acknowledged area of power noted by consumers during the research. Per the conducted interviews, crowd-based power was the power they felt was most compelling and was most acknowledged across questions and interview subjects. Network power was acknowledged as well on a smaller scale, specifically through the influencing of trends to one's network by means of what one wears or purchases. As with demand and sanction power, though a theoretically powerful tool, crowd and network-based power are one part of a multifaceted tool belt that must be well understood and readily utilized in order to move from the theoretically powerful space to the actually powerful space for consumers. Several interview subjects acknowledged the difficulty in utilizing this tool in response to Q5 with hedging statements such as "Together, yes. But the problem is getting them together" (R65, Q5).

Legitimate Power

The concept of legitimate power is a persuasive tool in service of the corporation and not in service of the consumer. Consumers acquiesce legitimacy easily to the corporation with bourgeois attitudes about keeping the peace and not questioning authority reinforcing this legitimacy.

Interview respondents did not acknowledge the consumerism construct and the ideas outside of that construct questioning whether consumption for consumption's sake must be a foregone conclusion. A significant respondent group spoke directly and without mitigation to the notion that they didn't believe they had any power relative to corporations, but no interview subject went as far as to question that overarching consumption ecosystem. This is a direct example of the consumer readily handing power legitimacy to the corporation.

This dynamic, paired with Foucault's discussion of subtle, masked power as an effective manner of power employment ensures a situation where the consumer is passively relieved of their power.

One Cannot See the Forest for the Trees

Consumers are so enmeshed in the consumption cycle and have assumed the identity of consumer so deeply that they fail to see outside of that context which is required to question one's role in it and thus utilize the greatest actual power afforded a consumer: the power to not consume. Through the interview research, no respondent questioned the dynamic of consumption to which consumers are subject. As mentioned, the respondents who did acknowledge the lack of power held by consumers in relation to the corporation did not take the further mental step to ask why this was the only available situational dynamic or react to their lack of power. All respondents took for granted their position as consumer and the assumed role consumers play in greater society. Respondents who answered affirmatively to the question of whether consumers had power defended their perceived power within the system despite many overt signals to the contrary. To be unable to question the conventional wisdom and current cultural dynamic around consumerism leaves consumers in a severely disadvantaged position relative to corporations.

Without the power to question the overall dynamic that consumers are subject to, consumers remain engrossed in a game that was built and maintained by the corporations and the rules for which are set by the corporations. The questioning of this dynamic is an enormous undertaking not to be understated and this research acknowledges the potential overwhelming challenges for consumers in thinking about such concepts.

Before the late 1970s, there still remained a cultural conversation regarding alternate options for economic viability, value creation, and cultural identity other than the current singular pathway of mass consumption. Generationally, we no longer have these diversified viewpoints where those alternative economic references or alternative pathways to success are top of mind or seem possible by the greater culture. Currently, a culture exists that only has experience within a society where metrics for success both culturally and economically are tied to consumption behaviors. This is perpetuated by the economic zeitgeist and pervasive academic work, initiated by Milton Friedman and maintained since by countless MBAs in the Chicago school of thought that now run institutions, corporations and think tanks, informing the greater culture that the only value to create is profit and that we as a culture and economy are entitled to ongoing, aggressive economic growth at any cost. These current ideas and norms leave behind the more

nuanced approach of Galbraith (1958), Mishan (1969), Marx (2017) and others mentioned whose ideologies temper the singular capitalistic pursuit of profits and consumption with other value metrics to offer a more diversified means to achieve success individually and as a society. The legacy of this singularly motivated school of thought has led to a relatively short-sighted view from subsequent forward-looking research. Most research exploring the power held by the consumer does not even consider the question of whether they have power to begin with, only whether the limited pathways afforded consumers are expanding to provide opportunity for increased consumer power through changes in technology and the manner of selling. These methods and research questions fail to view the situation from the proper distance necessary to see the actual dynamic: corporations control the dynamic and any power felt by consumers is orchestrated or managed by the power of the corporations. Consumers are afforded the opportunity to have more dialog with corporations, be heard more directly or even influence what product gets made (directly through co-creating or indirectly through exit) but ultimately are not afforded the power to exit the cycle entirely.

The Bourgeois Burden

Due to the modern Western cultural promise of upward mobility within individual lifetimes as well as continuation generation after generation, consumers feel entitled to access the bourgeois class and thus ignore red flags in their pursuit of that class participation. This belief is a relatively new concept that came with Western industrialization. As discussed by Galbraith in *The Affluent Society* (1958), previous to the last 150 years, nearly all of humanity through all recorded history could, at best, hope for the same opportunities year over year and generation over generation but would likely anticipate worse economic and social conditions. An entitlement to improved wealth and lifestyle was never on the table previous to the industrial revolution and the advent of consumerism. This puts consumers in a very difficult situation, making the questioning of their participation in consumption cycles nearly impossible as it would mean robbing themselves of the hope of greater wealth, even if that idea is unrealistic, ultimately unachievable, and has limited available evidence confirming the hope will be fulfilled.

With objects of fashion and style as signifiers, consumerism and fashion are the tools for class participation. Consumers are able to bridge the gap between their current social status and their desired social status through purchasing and brand alignment. These tools are widely used and nearly ubiquitous in their use as a cultural language within Western societies, and increasingly on a global scale. Though useful in seeking status, the tools of consumerism and fashion come with perils for consumers such as easy opportunities for overspending resulting in personal

debt. This peril is aided and masked by the previously mentioned promise of future increased prosperity and the entitlement to that future felt by consumers. Consumers mortgage the now for the assumed guaranteed payout of tomorrow, sacrificing any financial power they may have in order to class participate.

Further, good standing members of the bourgeoisie don't seek to make problems, they seek to conform. They behave civilly and are interested in maintaining the social order of societies because their position is maintained by and relative only to that social order. The modern bourgeoisie – the aspirational class – are aspirational only in that they create a lifestyle to be emulated exclusively through consumption habits. There are no active members of the aspirational class who are shirking consumerism and seeking ascetic existence outside the confines of traditional western capitalistic culture. Through emulation by other social classes, this modern bourgeoisie aids in perpetuating the cultural adoption of consumerist practices across all echelons of society.

Respondents within the research gave perfectly bourgeois answers, referencing their ability to influence trends (R4, Q2; R6, Q4; R36, Q2), show off status through purchases (R21, Q2; R35, Q2; R40, Q2; R41, Q2) and as mentioned before, the overall inability to question the dynamic of consumption. The research here reinforces that, in striving for the bourgeois class, consumers become trapped within their own norms and consumption habits and unwittingly reinforce the power afforded to corporations in their shared dynamic.

The Power of Conversation

The advent of technology has enabled greater dialog between consumers and corporations and as a result, despite ideas to the contrary, consumers have given up more power than they have gained in that transaction. As Foucault (1978) discusses and Barthes (2006) expands on, the discursive method is a great tool for those in power; the corporations seemingly give up control to enter a dialog where they listen to consumers but in actuality gain the advantage of insight and understanding of consumer motivations. This leads to the greater empowerment of corporations and a more disadvantaged position for the consumer. Consumers can be targeted in an increasingly specific manner by marketers and corporations and then manipulated based on the data they were willing to share with corporations in order to enter a dialog. The idea of co-creation and consumers working in tandem with companies to produce goods more aligned with what the consumer desires is explored as a new means of power for the consumer, facilitated through new available technologies; however, this perceived opportunity for the consumer again gives up more power than gained through the discursive power dynamic

previously mentioned. Further, this concept fails to recognize or contextualize the greatest underlying power of consumers: the power to not purchase. Contextualizing consumer power only within the framework of options of consumption fails to effectively zoom out and view the situation from the appropriate vantage point where the greatest and most powerful tools for power can be seen.

The Quicksand of Desire

Desire is an enslaving force and fashion consumption is predicated on a complicated web of consumer desires, ensnaring consumers in a dynamic that forces them to relinquish power in order to fulfill their desires. The consumer understands their desire for fashion and clothing as a means to self-identify and self-express through the language of fashion, participate in a culture greater than themselves, have physical signifiers for their own self-worth, and participate in the ongoing game of social status and class climbing. These desires are posed as a means for liberation but are actually the means and manner of their own entrapment and relinquishing of power. The greater a consumer's desire for the items mentioned above, the more enveloped in the consumption cycle the consumer becomes and the less power they ultimately have. The more fervently they pursue their own expression and individualism, the deeper in quicksand the consumer finds themselves, having given up their power and having become a tool within a framework of social control and political manipulation.

Vested Interest in the Consumer Power Myth

Corporations have a vested interest in perpetuating the myth of the powerful consumer. As discussed with clarity by Denegri-Knott, Zwick, and Schroeder (2006), the idea of the powerful consumer allows corporations and marketers to deflect their responsibility in the greater cultural dynamic of over consumption and consumerism. It relinquishes marketers and corporations from any responsibility they have for their use of seduction, coercion, and manipulation of the consumer in the pursuit of greater consumer purchasing.

The existence of this myth is also in service of the powerful corporation by way of Foucault's framework discussion of power maintenance. As discussed, power is most gripping when the party of less relative power believes themselves to be powerful and thus become complicit in the very power dynamic that perpetuates their disadvantaged position. When consumers are told and believe themselves to be powerful, they do the work of power reinforcement for the corporations even though it results in worse relative outcomes for themselves.

As the party of greater power, corporations are the producers and arbiters of truth in this context. Per Foucault (1978), truth can only be produced by power. Corporations use this power to produce a truth that reinforces the concept of the powerful consumer to allow for the continued and increased selling of goods, services, and ideas in a climate of unparalleled competition and reduced consumer need, ensuring the continued existence of the corporation and continued access to consumer's dollars.

Consumer Self-Deception

Consumers are interested in believing the myth of the powerful consumer. This is evidenced in the interview responses and conviction with which respondents answered in the affirmative regarding their power in relation to corporations. The struggle to rectify the want to be powerful and the reality of limited consumer power is evidenced in the disparity between quantitative affirmative responses and more qualitative expansions on those responses, particularly in research question Q2.

This idea is additionally reinforced by the academic research and the cultural conversation around the role of the consumer, both of which rarely question the foregone conclusion that the consumer is, of course, powerful. Studies and research have focused on a singular component of the consumer-corporation power dynamic, centered on one pathway to power and not the power dynamic as a whole. For example, since the wide scale adoption of the internet and its subsequent technologies, endless papers have been published discussing the growing power of the consumer by way of this technology including through increased access to information, access to competitive products, and consumer's ability to access corporations directly for discursive opportunity. At the risk of overusing a metaphor, this again is the greater culture not seeing the forest (in this case, greater consumer-corporation power dynamics) for the trees (in this case, greater opportunity within one potential consumer power tool). As discussed in an earlier section, these tools have the opportunity for greater power for consumers but in practice offer either as much, or more, power to corporations or are not being appropriately utilized by consumers thus offering no real improvement to the power position of consumers.

Why would an individual consumer, or consumers as a group, find it advantageous to question what the greater culture is telling them? The answer becomes clear when considering acknowledging the myth of consumer power would mean consumers would need to acquiesce to an inferior position, question their identity, personal value, and ability to acquire wealth and maintain a standard of living to which consumers feel entitled.

This element of consumer self-deception is a keystone component to the maintenance of the current powerful corporation and the less-than-powerful consumer dynamic. Per Foucault (1978), power cannot come from one central location and exert the necessary force to maintain power. It must radiate from myriad interconnected points, including from below, which in this case is the consumer themselves. In well situated power dynamics, there is no binary oppositional relationship between more powerful and less powerful or an exclusively top down dynamic. The power is duly reinforced by the well-behaved subjects in the positions of less relative power.

Conclusion

All of these analyses collectively dismantle the widely believed myth of the consumer as a powerful entity and master of their own destiny in capitalistic contexts. The consumer is not powerful relative to corporations; consumers have only an image or idea of power but not actual power. Through understanding the discussions of Foucault (1978), including the frameworks for the employment of power through sexuality, discourse, and desire, along with Barthes' (2006) arguments for fashion and clothing as language, it is evident that actual power lies with the fashion corporations and not with consumers. In selling both sexuality and desire, fashion corporations ensure their hold on power relative to consumers. Actual power is maintained through control of the desire. Corporations have the power as they provide the items of personal desire (in this case clothing and fashion as items for consumption), the opportunity for desire (in this case the greater stage/culture of fashion and style) and the means to be desired (again, in this case, the clothing itself, but as language).

Beyond Foucault (1978) and Barthes (2006), in the analyses of the components for understanding power by way of French and Raven (1959) as well as Magee and Galinsky (2008), it is clear the consumer does not have the greater power relative to corporations. Consumers have significantly less relative reward power than corporations; consumers can reward only with their business or their word of mouth endorsement of a brand through their networks. Corporations, on the other hand, have the power to reward consumers through attention, discounts and financial incentives, and the ability to award in-group status through brand alignment. The same argument applies to coercive power as corporations can retract the items of desire, leaving consumers with unfulfilled desires and an inability to communicate via fashion with the greater culture. Consumers in that same dynamic have the opportunity only to exit the corporation or brand, but as discussed, not the opportunity for complete exit from the greater consumption dynamic. Legitimate power is a particularly salient point in the argument against consumer power. Consumers acquiesce their power in several ways within their dynamic with corporations including in participating in overall fashion consumption and in seeking to fulfill desire through the means of fashion. Consumers not only acquiesce but also do the work of reinforcement by not questioning their assumed dynamic with corporations, leading to a strong legitimacy of power for the corporation and a complete absence of legitimate power for the consumer. Referent power is overwhelmingly in service of the corporations; consumers' need to brand align in order to class participate and find identity is a clear manifestation of the power corporations hold and use to engage consumers in cycles of consumption. Consumers

have no collective counterbalance to this one-sided referent dynamic. With expert power, consumers have no real opportunity to utilize this form of power relative to corporations as the balance of information is overwhelmingly in the hands of the corporation who has more resources to acquire information. Additionally, any consumer with enough knowledge to take on expert status reaches a tipping point where the expertise becomes a tool in service of the corporation as the consumer becomes a skill for the product or company for which they are an expert.

And lastly, all of this evidence builds an argument for the corporation ownership of actual power. Corporations functionally control the resources including the means and manufacture of clothing, the brand to which consumers align and buy into, the items to both desire and use as opportunities for desire, and the system in which these previous examples are made manifest, solidly proving the argument that the consumer is powerful relative to the fashion corporation incorrect.

Aside from the finer details of each type of power, the only types of power acknowledged by consumers as evidenced by the interviews conducted in this research, were reward and coercive power manifested through the power of consumer choice and consumer exit. As discussed, power unacknowledged is not power had, leaving the remaining theoretical executions of power at consumers' disposal unused by consumers and thus in service of the corporation. In reality, the consumer has only the role of consumer, and through all the above-mentioned definitions of power it is evident that the power that the interview subjects believe they have is not the forms of power identified. The only power consumers have is the power to purchase.

As understood through the concept of legitimate power, actual power is had when an entity controls the resources in a dynamic and corporations control the resources in their dynamic with consumers. The types and means of power the interview subjects discussed in this research were not the holistic picture of power per the definitions of French and Raven (1959) and Magee and Galinsky (2008). Consumers do not have actual power, only the idea of power. What they do have is the role of consumer and to be a successful consumer they must desire and seek to satiate that desire through purchasing. As Foucault (1978) showed, the more one desires, the more one has to surrender power in a dynamic. When consumers buy into prescribed consumption cycles because they see it as a tool for personal empowerment, they begin a journey seemingly in their favor and within their control but actually resulting in consumers systematically handing over their power to corporations. In their consumption, consumers

willingly surrender power to the corporation by way of money, information, attention, and continued participation in the corporation orchestrated mass-consumption dynamic. In this situation and amplified by their relationship to desire within the purchasing cycle of fashion and clothing, consumers are trapped in a descending spiral which progressively relinquishes them of any remaining power in their dynamic with corporations.

Though the information and argument necessary to deconstruct the myth of the powerful consumer is of major importance, it is a further requirement to understand that the myth is also the framework for the overall dynamic at play between consumer and corporation. Without the presence and strength of the myth of the powerful consumer, the dynamic of powerful corporations and powerless consumers cannot exist. To dissect this myth, all mentioned arguments are required but one must also have an understanding that the myth is supported by all stakeholders, including corporations, academia and the individual consumer, and to debunk the myth requires not only information and argument but understanding of motivations of the stakeholders who support the myth.

All stakeholders have a self-interested investment in the belief of the powerful consumer that itself reinforces the power of that belief making the battle to have an open conversation about this belief doubly difficult. Any effort to have a transparent dialog regarding this myth must tackle both the false belief as well as the power, money, and ego invested in that false belief, forcing stakeholders to abandon self-interest and put value in an untested potential where they likely will be required to give up a portion of their amassed power for a more egalitarian outcome that theoretically leads to an dynamic where “a rising tide lifts all boats” but could just as easily be perceived as a potential “zero sum game” for those in power.

Appendix A

Definitions

Consumer: An individual who buys goods or services for consumption.

Corporation: A for-profit company or brand engaged in selling a product, service, or idea.

Value Chain: "The full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the different phases of production, delivery to final consumers, and final disposal after use" (Kaplinsky & Morris, 2001, p.4).

Reward Power: The ability one individual has to offer rewards to another (French & Raven, 1959).

Coercive Power: The ability one individual has to offer punishments to another (French & Raven, 1959).

Legitimate Power: The perception of one individual that another individual has the right to exert power over them (French & Raven, 1959). Independent of actual power and made manifest through use of hierarchy (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Referent Power: Power exerted by one individual due to their identification with another individual

Expert Power: The perception that an individual has advanced knowledge granting them expert status (French & Raven, 1959).

Actual Power: Control of resources and their allocation (Magee & Galinsky, 2008).

Bourgeoisie: "The class of modern capitalists, owners of the means of social production" (Marx & Engels, 2017, p. 49).

Aspirational Class: Modern, well to do, educated elite that prize knowledge and cultural capital (Currid-Halkett, 2017).

Late Capitalism: Period beginning in the United States in the 1950s encompassing both economic and cultural structures. Marked by a post-modern culture, internationalization of business and banking, automation facilitated by technology, planned obsolescence, and American military and economic domination (Jameson, 1991).

Appendix B

Interview Data

Interviewer	Respondent	Gender	Location	Date	Q1 Binary	Q2 Qualitative	Q3 Binary	Q3 Qualitative	Q4 Binary	Q4 Qualitative	Q5 Binary	Q5 Qualitative	
I1	R1	F	Madison Square Park	5/17/2019	Y	Lois	N	-	Y	To a limited extent	Y	-	
I1	R2	F	Madison Square Park	5/17/2019	Y	Some	N	-	Y	-	Y	Definitely	
I1	R3	F	Madison Square Park	5/17/2019	Y	When we buy things with our money we are voting for how we want things to be made and so I really believe in trying to have more sustainable and like cruelty free clothing, shampoo and products so this is something I am willing to invest in	N	No they don't care about us	Y	Voting with dollars	Y	-	
I1	R4	F	Madison Square Park	5/17/2019	Y	We definitely set the trend. I feel like with our response, with our demand and our influence, we are the ones that are driving the products that we like this we prefer this and that sort of guides the trend.	N	So in a way the reason why I said No so quickly was because the word 'loyal' outside of the context of the brand means that you're in a way having a very compatible... it offers you what you want and you will also change according to their changes. So I feel like in that way they don't really need to like you. You probably like a pretty passive consumer	Y	With like bigger issues because recently I think in the political climate there are a lot of things that are being talked about and always very tied to those social issues and consumers we sort of have power in changing the way of expression especially if they're talking about a specific social issue that we care about. Like our responses will definitely affect their way of expression.	Y	Y	-
I1	R5	F	Madison Square Park	5/17/2019	Y	And also what celebrities are wearing, or like other like youubers or Instagrammers are like promoting these brands that affects us as well.	Y	I guess that the brands that I like, they have the stuff that I like.	Y	-	Y	-	
I1	R6	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	What power do I have as a fashion consumer? Well I think we have a lot of influence on the decisions. So personally, I think as an independent person I think I feel pretty good about that.	Y	I think it's interesting if's fashion and as a consumer they're trying to buy stuff that they like so they have to be interested in what I think about or what I'm interested in.	Y	Yes, I think that's possible because you always see the brands that are all over the sudden and so you know if all of a sudden you - I'm thinking more of my daughter's cohort - that you know they decide you know, and I've seen it with certain brands that they all of a sudden appear and then they disappear. I think it's super popular that everybody is wearing it. And I think it's with some things, shoes and stuff. It's brought back certain trends and certain shoes that were from like the 1980s because all of a sudden a bunch of 16-year-olds want to wear it.	Y	Y	Well I think it's sometimes if like if you know that a brand is using child labor, I think through social media I think yes you can
I1	R7	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	My power to buy something	N	No because generally they kind of care more about what's in, so that's where more of the kind of high fashion things and their kind of looking for what's new and the latest thing and I don't think they really take the time to ask the people, so to speak, about what they're wearing. They're taking like a generalized kind of survey. They're not, I dunno, I think it's just for certain brands they just don't care as much. But some do, it really depends.	Y	Minimal. We buy a lot of secondhand and that kind of stuff.	Y	Y	Again, kind of depends. We see more making changes but I think it's been a while coming.
I1	R8	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Quite a bit, I guess, especially if you are making smart choices with how you're purchasing fashion	Y	I would say they should be if they want to keep clients or customers	Y	-	Y	-	
I1	R9	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Money	N	I'm not really loyal to any fashion brands	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R10	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I am very good at finding very good deals.	N	I feel like the brands pretty much do their own thing and you buy it or not, I don't feel like I'm really loyal to any brands. I think maybe it's also because of the brands that I choose.	N	Because I don't give enough buying power. The power goes with the buying power. I think people are making more and more strong choices on the way that I choose and what I buy.	Y	Y	Oh yes. Brands just function...the economy...I mean they want people to buy what they want to sell.
I1	R11	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Not a lot	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R12	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	-	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R13	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	None	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R14	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	None	N	Hard no	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R15	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	None	Y	-	N	No, I think they operate us.	Y	-	
I1	R16	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	There's a lot of choices out there	Y	-	M	-	Y	-	
I1	R17	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Deciding whether to buy	N	-	M	Maybe. Whether you buy or not and how visible you are and how vocal you are about it.	Y	-	
I1	R18	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I would say the same (as R17)	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R19	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Not a whole lot, no.	Y	-	N	-	M	Maybe yes.	
I1	R20	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	None.	Y	-	N	-	M	Possibly.	
I1	R21	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I think I have the power of influence.	N	-	Y	-	Y	-	
I1	R22	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I don't know. I don't know if I have a whole lot of power.	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R23	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Oh yes. But I don't know why	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R24	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Yes, yes (to R23)	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R25	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	No power	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R26	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	No	N	-	N	-	Y	-	
I1	R27	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	A lot	Y	-	Y	-	Y	-	
I1	R28	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I agree (with R27)	Y	-	Y	-	Y	-	

Interviewer	Respondent	Gender	Location	Date	Q1 Binary	Q2	Q2 Qualitative	Q3 Binary	Q3 Qualitative	Q4 Binary	Q4 Qualitative	Q5 Binary	Q5 Qualitative
11	R29	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Yea [to R27], I feel there are so many options out there.		Y		M		Y	Possibly if you're talking about getting together hundreds of thousands of people.
11	R30	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	N	What she said [R31]		N		N		M	Possibly. Class action suits seem to do the trick.
11	R31	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Zero		N		N		M	I think that's what we need.
11	R32	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	N			Y		Y		M	I think that's what we need.
11	R33	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I think where it's made. It has an impact. Because if you buy something made in like Bangladesh, there's children.		Y		Y		Y	I think that's what we need.
11	R34	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I think you have to at least know where it's from and all that so, you can make a good choice		Y		Y		Y	A group has way more impact than alone
11	R35	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I do feel like there is a like an ambition to where you buy things. I think you should wear and everything has some element of power to it		N		N		Y	I think they can have a moderate sized one. I think you can get that. I think you can have that. I don't know if we see meaningful change from it. Like there's a - wherever there's an atrocity like in a Bhanditseshi factory, they all move their factories to temporarily to Vietnam or send the clothing to Luanta to have a tag sewn on there so they can't be traced back to Bangladesh. Like I do think there's an element of yes, people can change but I also think that like there is a lot of like competing for the bottom line and also trying to do damage control on reputation whenever something comes up, which I don't know if it will meaningfully change their life philosophy as a company
11	R36	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	N	The power to perpetuate a trend.		N		N		Y	You never know.
11	R37	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	N	No, I do not think much.		N		N		M	
11	R38	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	N	Not much.		N		N		M	Barely.
11	R39	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	And in fact I have an interest in design and I think that there's a lot out here and I don't know where all of this...this production that is already in existence is going to go so I can step back for a second and just say check out what's going on around me and all that		Y		Y		Y	
11	R40	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	Power? I guess by being a consumer, what you wear can inspire other people to go out and purchase it or inspire someone else's fashion sense or something along those lines		M		Y		Y	Absolutely, absolutely. If you even think about back to about a year ago when H&M had that whole big sink and everyone sort of boycotted them I think their sales dropped dramatically because of that and I've recently read an article where they had like over a million dollars worth of merchandise sitting in their warehouses. I don't know if it's because they're not used to that or if it's because they're used to it. So yea, consumers banding together. For sure.
11	R41	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	Yea, just the influence to kind of like show off what I bought, show off what I have maybe like influence another person to go out and buy something that I have or something similar from a similar store or whatever.		M		Y		Y	Most definitely, most definitely, I agree [with R40]
11	R42	M	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	Low power, if at all.		N		N		Y	
11	R43	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	When you like a brand and then you become brand loyal, then of course you have the power and if there is a defect or if there is a problem with the brand, you can report via social media, Instagram, and you know you have the power at the end of the day, I don't agree with my husband at all.		Y		N		Y	
11	R44	M	57th/5th	5/18/2019	N	None		N		N		Y	
11	R45	M	57th/5th	5/18/2019	N	None		N		N		Y	
11	R46	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	I have all the power, I choose.		N		N		Y	
11	R47	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	N	Yea, not much.		N		N		Y	
11	R48	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	N	Zero.		N		N		Y	
11	R49	F	57th/5th	5/18/2019	Y	Agreed [with R48]		N		Y		Y	
11	R50	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	None? Yea, none.		N		Y		Y	Absolutely.
11	R51	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	None.		N		N		Y	
11	R52	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	None		N		N		Y	Yes, if it's a big enough scale.
11	R53	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Very little, because I don't buy that much.		Y		N		Y	

Interviewer	Respondent	Gender	Location	Date	Q1 Binary	Q2 Qualitative	Q3 Binary	Q3 Qualitative	Q4 Binary	Q4 Qualitative	Q5 Binary	Q5 Qualitative
I1	R54	M	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	Yes, what she said [R55]	N	Not a chance. [In response to R55] They don't care about our preferences, they care about the mass preference as a whole.	N		Y	
I1	R55	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	I think you have the power with your dollars and so when you choose to spend your money kind of indicates where you have loyalty either towards a company or towards a particular lifestyle.	N	I'm not really loyal to them unless their cause is comparable and then I don't really like when you have something that you really like and you try to get another pair 2 years later, and they always charge it! A little bit, because somebody needs a job changing it.	-		Y	
I1	R56	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	We can decide where to go	N	You find something you really like and that you go with the trend, like oh everything's 2 inches shorter this year so they make it 2 inches shorter. For what?	-	Because if I don't like it, I'm not going to buy it, and I've done that with brands. They've changed their brand so I've switched to someone else and the more people do that they're not going to do that.	Y	
I1	R57	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	I buy what I want I'm not phased by what the trend is	N		-		Y	
I1	R58	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	I buy for comfort	N		-		Y	
I1	R59	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	We can pay what we want	N		-		Y	
I1	R60	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	A lot, I guess?	Y		-		Y	
I1	R61	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	Yes [to R60]	Y		-		Y	
I1	R62	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	I just like to dress for myself.	N	Probably not, no.	-		Y	Yes, that would work
I1	R63	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	I don't think they really care	N		-		Y	Yes, if everyone was to stop buying from a certain place, then they would have to change and adapt to our needs
I1	R64	M	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Yes, probably the same [as R65]	N	I don't think I'm really loyal to any brands. But probably not, also.	-		Y	Together, yes. But the problem is getting them together.
I1	R65	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	I worked retail for a really long time so I know the power of the consumer but individually, not that much	N	Maybe like smaller brands that I spend a lot of money on because I get like the surveys like the anonymous surveys cause they're like wow you spend a lot of money here but in general, no probably not.	-		Y	
I1	R66	M	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Probably very small.	N		-	Individually no. I think if everybody that way, like if it was a society - yes. But individually, no.	Y	
I1	R67	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Yes, I would like so [in response to R66]	N		-		Y	
I1	R68	M	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Very little.	Y		-		Y	
I1	R69	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Not that much.	Y		-		Y	
I1	R70	M	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	Low	Y		-		Y	
I1	R71	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	No, Low	Y	Some brands, yes.	-		Y	
I1	R72	M	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	N	No power at all	N	Not really.	-		Y	
I2	R73	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	All the power. We have the right to consume as we want to. So we can either consume smart or consume ignorantly so it's all within our power	Y	From my point of view, I have a tendency to buy less but buy better. The brands that I am a fan of and am a proponent of are all products that I don't really care about and I'm really looking to know where they manufacture, how the item is made and the ethos behind that because at this point I don't need to have things in my wardrobe that I'm really using. I think they have better quality and just more behind it so that it's going to last longer and eventually it will have some value once I'm done with it so that I can put it back into the world and have it be used by someone else. I don't think there's not to recycle but to make sure that the garment continues having a history post me as a consumer.	Y	I think it needs to be a large enough voice, a large group, and it needs to be united in what the goal is and how to achieve it. Like sometimes you can't just say, as a reality check, we need to be sustainable and we need to be ethical, but we need to figure it out on how that can be achieved. Or like, I think we as like being a part of that conversation we can't just have demands we also have to like give ideas on like how to accomplish that. Or put together an agenda for a group or a leader. I know because I've been in that space. I think it's a productive conversation. It's not a conversation.	Y	
I2	R74	F	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	There are some limits, some caveats. Wanting to look good but also being like ath price does matter. So I think that's important. It's not like it's a matter of priorities, and I could shift my priorities	Y	I feel like I am loyal to like 3 brands. I think those 3 are like pretty aware of me. And then there are some that are guilty and I don't really buy from them. But I'll shop there. And I've had bad about it.	-		Y	Along those same lines, I think there are times when brands are like, oh we're like environmentally friendly and you're like you're lying to me - you think that is a demand but you're not being real. You're like, like we know or the human impact of the people you're lying or whatever.
I2	R75	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	N	Not very much individually, but collectively, if everyone were able to mobilize then we would.	Y	They'll catch on to certain trends or whatnot. I guess for instance, Nike these sort of shoes are making a comeback so I guess they're sort of conscious of like consumer trends and what we're looking for at any given time.	N	Probably not	Y	
I2	R76	M	60th/5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	If I don't believe in what the producer stands for what they're doing, the things are produced I don't buy from them. Purchasing power I suppose	Y		N	Not individually, collectively I think we do. If we were vocal about something as consumers, as a group of consumers. Especially if we are vocal.	Y	

Interviewer	Respondent	Gender	Location	Date	Q1 Binary	Q2 Qualitative	Q3 Binary	Q3 Qualitative	Q4 Binary	Q4 Qualitative	Q5 Binary	Q5 Qualitative
I2	R77	F	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Actually all the power if they didn't have no consumers then there won't be no fashion.	N	It's a business	N	At this stage of life, no. Everything is already branded to the people, so it's set as the way it is.	Y	
I2	R78	F	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Zero	N	-	N	He'll no.	N	I guess if there were enough negative brought in front of them, then yes but it would have to be a lot of people. A lot of people with a lot of money.
I2	R79	F	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Zero	N	-	N	You got to be somebody to do that, not the little people.	N	
I2	R80	F	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	None. I think age has a lot to do with it. I think at my age in particular my fashion style is pretty much set so influenced by fashion these days doesn't mean anything.	Y	They gear towards my age and fashion that's appropriate	N	As an individual? No. But as a group, maybe. But you have to be able to speak up and say something.	Y	
I2	R81	M	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	-	N	Never.	N	Not one person. But many people thinking the same can change something.	Y	
I2	R82	F	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I have all of the power. Companies have to market in order for me to purchase so in order to keep the companies profitable, as they have to market to me. I think that's most essential based from the appeal of the brand and design.	N	-	N	I believe I have the ability to impact how they are viewed by other consumers but that doesn't necessarily mean that I can control how they operate. WORK, social media.	Y	An effect certainly, but measurable? Who is doing the measuring? Is it the corporation?
I2	R83	M	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Everything right now is just a big trend. You know? and you can either...I don't know. Now that you asked that it's funny because the trends kind of make themselves. I mean you can't really purchase into it or you don't but like the way that trends work as a consumer you don't have too much, it's more or less what's advertised.	Y	-	Y	-	Y	Especially now with social media. It becomes, everything becomes a movement. Reaction lines with companies want everything need to be much, know because there is much more scrutiny. So I feel yes.
I2	R84	M	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	You don't make the trend you just follow it or now.	Y	-	Y	It depends on the brand. Not all brands will focus actually on the actual customers. They'll focus on the trends. They'll make what they think is going to be popular and put it out there and then it goes to what he said [R83] you either follow it, you buy it or you don't buy it.	Y	Not me personally, consumers can. As a group, not an individual.
I2	R85	M	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	I personally don't think I have any power. Any. I usually go into a store and buy what I like. But I don't really have an input into what they make.	Y	-	N	Not personally, but if enough people get together.	Y	
I2	R86	F	60th&5th Ave	5/18/2019	Y	Moderate power.	Y	-	N	It all starts somewhere.	Y	
I2	R87	M	57th&5th	5/18/2019	Y	Agree [R86]	N	Ideally we should hope, but they don't. The process, there's no connection for that to happen.	Y	I feel I am a very empowered consumer.	Y	
I2	R88	F	57th&5th	5/18/2019	Y	All of the power. You can't make a big statement than not spending money in a store. If you don't buy things than people aren't going to change.	Y	I think brands care.	Y		Y	
I2	R89	M	57th&5th	5/18/2019	Y	I think that as an individual it's tough to feel that you have a ton of power but if you're part of a group that is say boycotting a brand or something like that it's a lot more powerful. But I know that like walk into Macy's going to one brand vs the other I don't feel that I have a ton of power in that sense. I think that's going to effect things in a broader sense.	N	Only to the point where it helps them make a profit. Like if I wanted them to be more sustainable or have better labor practices but like if they're not going to do that, I think they're not going to do that.	N	I think it is a thing of scale. If there are movements or organizations and the general sentiment towards a brand that's tough because small pockets or one person or a small group of people choosing not to wear a brand isn't going to have the effect you need to see. It comes down to money at the end of the day.	Y	Scale is the only way that you can get an effect.
I2	R90	F	57th&5th	5/18/2019	Y	For an individual picking and choosing you have that sense of power but if you belong to a community or group then likewise. That being a little more influential in terms of exercising any type of change.	N	-	N	The foundation of the company plays a role and their mission to begin with. If it does have more of a focus of like sustainability or activism in that way then maybe they'd be more open but other than that I don't think so.	Y	
I2	R91	M	57th&5th	5/18/2019	Y	I don't think I have consumer power or that I can influence anyone. I don't think I can influence anyone.	Y	Social media has a lot to do with it. If you're not on social media they'll change it for us. Nike does this.	Y	Just by being honest about the things that you're not happy about their states will go down.	Y	
I2	R92	F	Rockefeller Center	5/18/2019	Y	I mean I don't know. I don't think I have any power. Because I'm not in the industry. I'm not a creative in that sense. I don't think there is someone out there looking to see what fashion I want to wear.	N	They don't survey me	Y	If I were given opportunity to possibly give some input about what type of things they are creating. But it's already pre-done. A year in advance. Whatever is already getting ready to come out for the fall has already been in the mix for 2 years prior.	Y	
I1	R93	F	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	Very little	M	Somewhat	M	Maybe if they directly ask me.	Y	
I1	R94	F	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	Very little	N	-	Y	I have never had a brand give me a survey or ask my opinion.	Y	
I1	R95	F	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	Very little. I just have to accept it.	N	-	N	-	Y	
I1	R96	M	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	None	N	-	N	-	Y	
I1	R97	M	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	You could just choose to stop second hand.	Y	Yes, until there is someone to replace me	Y	In a tiny way	Y	

Interviewer	Respondent	Gender	Location	Date	Q1 Binary	Q2 Binary	Q2 Qualitative	Q3 Binary	Q3 Qualitative	Q4 Binary	Q4 Qualitative	Q5 Binary	Q5 Qualitative
11	R98	F	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	Y	I think that we do have the power to choose. You know if I either want to buy something that is like plastic or not or, I don't want to buy it, I can go somewhere I spend my money. I don't think that necessarily dictates the kind of like factories or the work that is done but it's something	M	Yes and no. Yes because they want to sell to you and so they want to market to what you're buying but then I think no because I don't think that the market or what evolve is to set the next standard or trend	N	Collectively yes, individually no	Y	
11	R99	M	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	N	Little to none	N		N		Y	
11	R100	M	Wyckoff/Trouman	5/19/2019	Y	N	same thing	N		N	Possibly but no	Y	

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